

Master Thesis

**Advancing the Neural SBI toolkit for SMEFT
analyses**

by

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Advancing the Neural SBI toolkit for SMEFT analyses

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Abstract. The Large Hadron Collider (LHC) produces around a billion proton-proton collisions per second, generating complex, high dimensional data that demand advanced analysis techniques. In this work, we explore Transformer architectures to perform neural simulation-based inference (NSBI) on Standard Model Effective Field Theory (SMEFT) parameters. Traditional inference methods in high-energy physics rely on low-dimensional summaries, limiting sensitivity to model parameters. NSBI instead exploits multivariate information by training neural networks to approximate likelihood ratios and likelihood gradients (scores) from simulated data. We adapt the Lorentz Geometric Algebra Transformer (LGATr), a Lorentz equivariant architecture for particle data, to regress both likelihood ratios and scores for SMEFT Wilson coefficients estimation. Additionally, we provide a non-equivariant Transformer with matched architecture to assess the impact of the inductive bias introduced in LGATr. We compare our implementations to traditional methods based on histograms and baseline multilayer perceptron architectures. We tested our methods in both a one- and three-dimensional analysis. The sensitivity improvements of self-attention-based architectures become more clear in the higher dimensional analysis, which highlights their potential in more realistic scenarios. In particular, we find score regressors to be more robust, while likelihood ratio regressors struggle to learn the theory parameters dependency in higher dimensions. Despite the simplicity of the physical scenarios considered, these findings pave the way to a deep learning based approach for SMEFT parameter estimation.

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1 Introduction

At the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), beams of protons collide head-on, leading to around a billion proton-proton interactions per second [37,23]. High-precision detectors surround the interaction point to capture signals from collision debris, recording around 1 gigabyte of data per second [29,32]. The next generation High Luminosity LHC is expected to increase the total number of collisions by at least an order of magnitude [17], further enabling statistically meaningful studies of rare processes. Each of these collisions, or *events*, is characterized by a high number of emerging particles reconstructed from the detector signals. The high dimensionality and amount of data in LHC analyses make them perfect candidates to benefit from deep learning (DL) techniques [30,9,21]. In particular, Transformers have attractive properties for high-energy physics (HEP) data: they can process particle sets of varying multiplicity in a length-agnostic manner, are equivariant with respect to permutations of particles in an event, and scale well to large datasets. Their efficacy has already been demonstrated in several HEP tasks [16,39,26]. Recently, a multi-purpose Transformer architecture for HEP data equivariant with respect to Lorentz transformations, the symmetry group of spacetime, was introduced [36, LGATr]. In this work, we present adaptations of (equivariant) Transformers architectures for HEP data to perform inference on theory parameters using simulated data.

The enormous scientific effort carried out at the LHC seeks to probe the limitations of the Standard Model (SM) of particle physics. Searches for new physics, i.e., physics not explained by the SM, compare collision data with synthetic data generated with the aid of precise theory calculations and Monte Carlo (MC) simulators. Assuming a parametrized theory model, we compare observations with data sampled from different parameter hypothesis to draw conclusions (set bounds) on the validity of our theory.

Simulations in HEP are only run in forward mode, i.e., we can sample data according to a certain theory hypothesis $x \sim p(x | \theta)$ but given observed data x_{obs} we have no way to calculate the likelihood $p(x_{\text{obs}} | \theta)$. This problem is further complicated by the high dimensionality of both HEP data and the parameter space, and by the non-trivial correlations between different parameters.

Traditional inference methods rely on low dimensional summaries of the data, losing multivariate information for parameter estimation. Multivariate methods based on neural networks address this limitation working in the whole input space, retaining maximum sensitivity to changes in θ . Fixing a reference hypothesis θ_{ref} , we use simulated data sampled from different parameter hypotheses to train estimators that regress likelihood ratios $r(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ or other quantities related to the likelihood. Once trained, we can perform inference on the theory parameters using the estimated likelihood ratios. This inference technique, i.e., training neural networks with simulated data to perform inference on theory parameters, fits under the general neural simulation-based

inference (NSBI) framework. See Fig. 1 for an illustration of the steps described above.

Foundational work for likelihood ratio regression in HEP was introduced for Standard Model effective field theory (SMEFT) analyses, condensed in the MADMINER framework [38,18,11]. SMEFT expands the SM with a series of higher-dimensional operators, associated with a set of free parameters, the *Wilson coefficients* of the theory. They introduced multilayer perceptron (MLP) architectures to regress likelihood ratios and scores, i.e., the gradient of the likelihood function with respect to the theory parameters. Although several studies have been published using the techniques introduced in MADMINER [27,35,5], the potential of modern DL architectures for the estimation of SMEFT parameters remains largely unexplored.

In this work, our aim is to reduce the gap between the development of machine learning (ML) architectures for the Wilson coefficients inference problem and those introduced for other HEP tasks. More specifically, we adapt (equivariant) Transformer architectures to perform inference on the Wilson coefficients of SMEFT. We introduce an adaptation of LGATr for the likelihood ratio regression and score regression problems and provide a non-equivariant Transformer with a matched architecture for comparison. We compare our methods with baseline MLP architectures and traditional methods based on histograms. We tested our methods in both a one- and three-dimensional analysis. We find that the sensitivity improvements of self-attention-based architectures become more clear in the higher dimensional analysis, which highlights their potential in more realistic (global) scenarios. In particular, we find score regressors to be more robust, while likelihood ratio regressors struggle to learn the theory parameters dependency in higher dimensions and suffer from high numerical instability.

Fig. 1: Neural-based likelihood ratio estimation. First, we choose a theory parameter basis to sample simulated events from. We then use these events to train likelihood ratio (or score) regressors. Finally, we use the trained estimators to set limits on the theory parameters using test data. Adapted from [20].

The reproducibility code is available on <https://github.com/arturoam00/tzq-sbi-ml>.

2 Background

Searches for new physics in an *effective* way

The Standard Model (SM) of particle physics is a quantum field theory that models all known elementary particles and their interactions. Despite the success of its predictions, it has several phenomenological and theoretical limitations. On the empirical side, it does not incorporate gravity, does not contain dark matter or dark energy, and treats neutrinos as massless, which disagrees with experimental observations. On the theory side, it does not offer an explanation for the number of generations or for the apparent fine-tuning of its many free parameters, to name a few.

Searches for new physics, or physics beyond the Standard Model (BSM), traditionally look for new particles using specific theory models, e.g., Supersymmetry or Composite Higgs models, which require on-shell production of the new resonances at the current kinematic reach of our colliders, i.e., at the few TeV scale. The absence of findings in these kind of searches has motivated Standard Model effective field theory (SMEFT) indirect searches. SMEFT treats the SM as a low-energy limit of a more fundamental (unknown) theory, extending its theoretical description with higher dimensional operators, consistent with the SM fields and symmetries, suppressed by powers of a heavy energy scale Λ . This cut-off scale must be well above the electroweak energy scale, so $\Lambda \gg m_h$,¹ since otherwise new physics would have already been seen at the LHC [33]. For the purposes of our analyses, we restrict ourselves to operators of mass-dimension 6 (see A.1 for justification). In this case, the Lagrangian reads

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SMEFT}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}} + \sum_i^{N_{d6}} \frac{c_i}{\Lambda^2} \mathcal{O}_i^{(6)}. \quad (1)$$

The coefficients c_i , known as *Wilson coefficients*, are free parameters of the theory, and by constraining them with experimental data we put bounds on BSM physics: a statistically significant deviation of any c_i from 0 would constitute evidence for new physics.

In this framework, we probe new physics indirectly through deviations in SM processes that are sensitive to high-energy effects, without assuming specific BSM models or requiring direct production of heavy particles. See Fig. 2a for an illustration of this.

¹ Although the current Run 3 of the LHC has a center-of-mass energy of 13.6 TeV, parton-parton collisions happen at the electroweak energy scale (~ 100 GeV).

Fig. 2: *Left*: Traces of new physics at high energies produce subtle modifications of observables distributions, which can be studied evaluating the deviations from the known theory in the effective field theory (EFT) region. Adapted from [41]. *Right*: Distribution of the transverse momentum (p_T) of the first sub-leading jet in tZ production for different values of the Wilson coefficient c_{Ht} and for the SM value ($c_{Ht} = 0.0$).

$tZ(j)$ production at the LHC

One promising process for new physics searches with SMEFT is $tZ(j)$ production at the LHC. Since the top quark is much heavier than all other known SM fermions, new physics at higher energy scales could manifest at lower energies through the top quark’s effective interactions, making potential deviations from SM predictions observable [44]. In particular, $tZ(j)$ probes a focused set of electroweak SMEFT operators [19], with a distinct $3\ell + b\text{-jet} + E_T^{\text{miss}}$ signature that makes it experimentally accessible [1]. We test our methods in this process, focusing on the set of dimension-six operators $\{\mathcal{O}_{tW}, \mathcal{O}_{tB}, \mathcal{O}_{Ht}\}$,² associated with the corresponding set of Wilson coefficients $\{c_{tW}, c_{tB}, c_{Ht}\}$, all of which modify the interaction between the top quark and the Z boson (\mathcal{O}_{tW} also modifying the $W - t - b$ vertex), and are relatively weakly constrained [2,34,19]. See Fig. 3 for an illustration of a representative Feynman diagram of the process and Fig. 2b for an example of the kind of modifications that different values for the Wilson coefficients induce in the event-level observables.

Simulations at the LHC and probability model

Simulations of events at the LHC consist of theoretical calculations and a chain of MC simulators. Given the theory model, e.g., the SMEFT Lagrangian with

² \mathcal{O}_{Ht} is also noted $\mathcal{O}_{\phi t}$, and then the corresponding coefficient is $c_{\phi t}$.

Fig. 3: Feynman diagram illustrating one of the leading order (LO) t-channel contributions to tZq production at the LHC. The initial b quark originates from gluon splitting ($g \rightarrow b\bar{b}$) from one of the colliding protons and the initial light quark q comes from the other proton. They interact exchanging a virtual W boson, turning the b quark into a top quark, which then radiates a Z boson. Because of its short average lifetime, the top quark decays then via weak interaction before hadronization, producing a W boson and a b quark. The red dots indicate the insertion points of the SMEFT operators \mathcal{O}_{tW} (both points), \mathcal{O}_{tB} and \mathcal{O}_{Ht} (rightmost point).

a chosen subset of dimension 6 operators, and a set of values for the model parameters θ , e.g., a set of values for the Wilson coefficients, for a process of interest, e.g., $tZ(j)$, we first calculate the Feynman diagrams up to a certain order, which give the scattering amplitudes \mathcal{M} . We use MC to sample from $|\mathcal{M}|^2$, generating parton-level events $z_p \sim p(z_p | \theta)$. We then simulate shower effects and hadronization, also with MC, giving $z_s \sim p(z_s | z_p)$. We simulate the detector effects and obtain $z_d \sim p(z_d | z_s)$. Lastly, we simulate object reconstruction and observable creation, obtaining the desired simulated events $x \sim p(x | z_d)$. These steps are illustrated in Fig. 4. We can write the probability model of this simulation chain as

$$p(x | \theta) = \int dz_d dz_s dz_p \underbrace{p(x | z_d)p(z_d | z_s)p(z_s | z_p)p(z_p | \theta)}_{p(x, z_d, z_s, z_p | \theta) \equiv p(x, z | \theta)}. \quad (2)$$

The space spanned by the latent variables z_d , z_s and z_p can have dimensions up to $\sim 10^9$ [13], making an analytical calculation of the integrals impossible. LHC analyses are based on simulation-based inference techniques to deal with the intractability of the likelihood function.

Inference pipeline at the LHC

Here, we present the traditional inference pipeline for hypothesis testing at the LHC. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^N \equiv \{x\}$ be a set of i.i.d. events (observed or simulated) sampled as $x_i \sim p(x_i | \theta)$. Assuming that the total number of events N is itself a random

Fig. 4: Simulation chain at the LHC. We fix the theory parameters θ to calculate the corresponding Feynman diagrams and associated scattering amplitudes. We simulate shower, hadronization and detector response before constructing the desired events x . Adapted from [7,31]

(Poisson) variable with expected value $\nu(\theta)$, the likelihood reads

$$p(\{x\} | \theta) = \text{Pois}(N | \nu(\theta)) \prod_{i=1}^N p(x_i | \theta).$$

As mentioned earlier, traditional methods construct summary statistics of the data $f(x)$, to deal with the high dimensionality. Therefore, after the summaries,

$$p(\{x\} | \theta) = \text{Pois}(N | L\sigma(\theta)) \prod_{i=1}^N p(f(x_i) | \theta).$$

Here we have substituted the expected number of events by $L\sigma(\theta)$. L represents the integrated luminosity, which combined with the total cross section $\sigma(\theta)$ gives the total number of expected events. Typically, simulated data are used to create one dimensional summary statistics histograms for different hypotheses, approximating the probability density function (PDF) of $f(x)$. Then, using new (test) data, we can calculate the (approximated) likelihood of each event given the parameter as

$$\hat{p}_{\text{hist}}(f(x_i) | \theta) = \frac{N_b}{N_{\text{tot}}\Delta_b},$$

where b is the histogram bin in which x_i falls, N_b is the number of events used to create the histogram contained in bin b , N_{tot} is the total number of events used to create the histogram and Δ_b is the width of the bin.³ The likelihood then reads

$$p(\{x\} | \theta) = \text{Pois}(N | L\sigma(\theta)) \prod_{i=1}^N \hat{p}_{\text{hist}}(f(x_i) | \theta) \quad (3)$$

³ If we fit the histogram with a smooth function (assuming a parametric *ansatz*), then $\hat{p}(x_i | \theta) = F_{\text{ansatz}}(f(x_i) | \theta)$.

Hypothesis testing Consider a null parameter hypothesis θ and a fixed reference hypothesis θ_{ref} . We consider the *likelihood ratio test* for the null hypothesis, characterized by the likelihood ratio test statistic. The *profile* likelihood ratio reads

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda(\theta) &= -2 \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{p(x_i | \theta)}{p(x_i | \hat{\theta})} = -2 \sum_{i=1}^N \log r(x_i | \theta, \hat{\theta}) = \\ &= -2 \sum_{i=1}^N \log r(x_i | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}}) - \log r(x_i | \hat{\theta}, \theta_{\text{ref}}),\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\hat{\theta} = \arg \max_{\theta \in \Omega} \sum_{i=1}^N \log r(x_i | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}}).$$

Ω represents the entire parameter space. According to Wilks theorem [43], under standard regularity conditions and under the null hypothesis (θ true), the distribution $p(\lambda(\theta) | \theta)$ tends to a chi-squared distribution as the sample size tends to ∞ , with degrees of freedom k equal to the number of parameters. This allows us to construct confidence intervals for the MLE, calculating the p -values for observed values of the test statistic $\lambda_{\text{obs}}(\theta)$ as

$$p_{\theta} \equiv \int_{\lambda_{\text{obs}}(\theta)}^{\infty} d\lambda p(\lambda | \theta) = 1 - F_{\chi^2}(\lambda(\theta) | k), \quad (4)$$

where $F_{\chi^2}(x | k)$ is the cumulative distribution of the chi-squared distribution with k degrees of freedom.

We introduced the SMEFT framework and motivated our physics example process. We showed the intractability of the likelihood function in LHC analyses and a way to approximate it using histogrammed summary statistics, as well as how to construct confidence intervals using the likelihood ratio in a frequentist approach. We now see how we can use machine learning to exploit multivariate information of events and retain maximum sensitivity to changes in θ .

(Neural) simulation based inference

Simulation based inference (SBI) is a collection of methods that estimate model parameters when the likelihood function is not available or prohibitively expensive to compute. This is often the case in fields of science where highly complex, stochastic simulators produce synthetic data given a (parametrized) theory model. The simulation data are compared with real observations to draw conclusions about the validity of the underlying model and the values of the constraint parameter. Neural simulation based inference (NSBI) allows for this comparison by training neural networks (NNs) to perform inference on observed data. This process consists of the following steps: 1. First, we choose

a set of model parameters to simulate the data. If we have access to prior distributions, we can sample $\theta \sim p(\theta)$. 2. Second, we run the simulator in forward mode to generate synthetic data $x \sim p(x | \theta)$. 3. We then train a neural network with the samples (x, θ) to estimate the likelihood, some related quantity (like the likelihood ratio), or, in a Bayesian setting, the posterior distribution $p(\theta | x)$. When estimating the posterior, we can assume that it is Gaussian in the simplest case, and then the network is trained to regress its mean and variance. The problem of estimating the likelihood ratio can be reframed as a classification problem [18, CARL]. 4. Finally, we perform inference on the observed data x_{obs} . Importantly, inference here is *amortized*: once the networks are trained, they can estimate posteriors for new observations without need to be retrained or more simulations [20]. Limits for the predictions are naturally set for the case of regressing posterior distributions. In the case of the likelihood ratio, we can use the asymptotic properties introduced above. See Fig. 1 for an illustration of the steps.

In the next section, we present how to train multivariate methods to regress likelihood ratios, with the goal of improving the sensitivity of the inference pipeline at the LHC. Although we could use CARL, we demonstrate how to exploit the factorization of the likelihood ratio to extract valuable information from the simulations. This was first introduced in MADMINER [11].

3 Methods

In this section, we describe the methodology for our analyses. We address the concepts needed to understand the following pipeline, which is the core of our work: 1. We choose a theory parameter basis to sample physical events using a morphing technique. 2. We run the simulation chain in forward mode and extract joint likelihood ratios (scores) from the simulator, exploiting the likelihood factorization and the morphing technique. These quantities are used as regression labels to define loss functionals that approximate the true likelihood ratio (score). 3. We train estimators using the derived loss functionals. Estimators that regress (log) likelihood ratios are *parametrized*, that is, they take the model parameters as input (in addition to the data). 4. We use test data sampled according to a reference parameter hypothesis and calculate the likelihood ratio test statistic on different points of a parameter grid using the trained estimators, obtaining a MLE point and confidence intervals using Wilks. This process is illustrated in Fig. 1.

In Section 3.1 we present how to extract joint likelihood ratios and scores from the simulator, and how they are used to define loss functionals that, when minimized, approximate the true quantities. In Section 3.2 we introduce the morphing technique and how it is used to calculate likelihood ratios and scores. In Section 3.3 we present the estimator architectures used. Finally, in Section 3.4 we describe the evaluation procedure.

3.1 Simulation-derived training labels

We explain how to exploit the factorization of the likelihood in LHC processes shown in Eq. (2) to extract quantities from the simulator that can be used to train (log) likelihood ratio and score regressors. These quantities are the joint likelihood ratio and the joint score. The key points to note are: 1. Our MC simulators are not a “black-box” but contain information about the latent variables used to generate their outcomes. 2. It can be demonstrated that the joint likelihood ratio (score) can be used to construct loss functionals that, when minimized, approximate the true likelihood ratio (score).

Extracting information from the simulations We start by noting that the term $p(z_p | \theta)$ in Eq. (2) is available from the simulator. This is the normalized differential cross section at parton level

$$p(z_p | \theta) = \frac{1}{\sigma(\theta)} \frac{d\sigma(z_p | \theta)}{dz_p}.$$

For a LHC process, $d\sigma$ takes the form [4]

$$d\sigma(z_p | \theta) = \frac{(2\pi)^4 f_1(x_1, Q^2) f_2(x_2, Q^2)}{2x_1 x_2 s} |\mathcal{M}(z_p | \theta)|^2 d\Phi(z_p). \quad (5)$$

In Eq. (5), x_1 and x_2 are the momentum fractions carried by initial-state partons, $f_i(x_i, Q^2)$ the parton density functions, s is the center-of-mass energy, Q the momentum transfer and $d\Phi(z_p)$ the Lorentz-invariant phase-space element. Most importantly, $|\mathcal{M}|^2$ is the *squared matrix element*, calculated from the theory Lagrangian in the simulations and enclosing the dependence on θ . Having noted that the (evaluated) $d\sigma/dz_p$, from now on referred to as *event weight* w , is available from the simulator, we consider the *joint likelihood ratio* between two hypotheses θ and θ_{ref} , defined as

$$\begin{aligned} r(x, z | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}}) &\equiv \frac{p(x, z_d, z_s, z_p | \theta)}{p(x, z_d, z_s, z_p | \theta_{\text{ref}})} \\ &= \frac{p(x | z_d) p(z_d | z_s) p(z_s | z_p) p(z_p | \theta)}{p(x | z_d) p(z_d | z_s) p(z_s | z_p) p(z_p | \theta_{\text{ref}})} \\ &= \frac{p(z_p | \theta)}{p(z_p | \theta_{\text{ref}})} = \frac{\sigma(\theta_{\text{ref}})}{\sigma(\theta)} \frac{d\sigma(z_p | \theta)}{d\sigma(z_p | \theta_{\text{ref}})} = \frac{\sigma(\theta_{\text{ref}})}{\sigma(\theta)} \frac{|\mathcal{M}(z_p | \theta)|^2}{|\mathcal{M}(z_p | \theta_{\text{ref}})|^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The intractable factors of the likelihood cancel out when taking ratios because they do not depend on the theory parameters, making **the joint likelihood ratio tractable**.

Defining loss functionals We start by considering the L^2 loss functional for a learnable estimator $f_\phi(x)$ with network parameters ϕ that tries to approximate

a function $f(x, z)$

$$\begin{aligned} L[f_\phi(x)] &= \int dx dz p(x, z | \tilde{\theta}) |f(x, z) - f_\phi(x)|^2 = \\ &= \int dx \underbrace{\left[f_\phi^2(x) \int dz p(x, z | \tilde{\theta}) + \int dz p(x, z | \tilde{\theta}) f^2(x, z) - 2f_\phi(x) \int dz p(x, z | \tilde{\theta}) f(x, z) \right]}_{F(x)} \end{aligned}$$

where we omitted the conditioning of $f(x, z | \theta)$ and $f_\phi(x | \theta)$ in θ for a cleaner notation. Minimizing $F(x)$ with respect to $f_\phi(x)$ leads to the optimal function f_ϕ^* , i.e, the function that extremizes the functional $L[f_\phi(x)]$

$$0 = \left. \frac{\delta F}{\delta f_\phi} \right|_{f_\phi^*} = 2f_\phi(x) \int dz p(x, z | \tilde{\theta}) - 2 \int dz p(x, z | \tilde{\theta}) f(x, z),$$

so

$$f_\phi^*(x) = \frac{1}{p(x | \tilde{\theta})} \int dz p(x, z | \tilde{\theta}) f(x, z). \quad (7)$$

Identifying $f(x, z)$ with the joint likelihood ratio $r(x, z | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ and doing $\tilde{\theta} = \theta_{\text{ref}}$

$$f_\phi^*(x) = \frac{1}{p(x | \theta_{\text{ref}})} \int dz p(x, z | \theta_{\text{ref}}) \frac{p(x, z | \theta)}{p(x, z | \theta_{\text{ref}})} = r(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}}). \quad (8)$$

Note that $f(x, z)$ can be any affine transformation of the joint likelihood ratio since such operations commute with the integral in Eq. (8). Let $f_\phi(x) \equiv r_\phi(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$. By minimizing

$$L[r_\phi(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})] = \left\langle [r(x, z | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}}) - r_\phi(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})]^2 \right\rangle_{(x, z) \sim p(x, z | \theta_{\text{ref}})}$$

we regress on the true likelihood ratio $r(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$. This argument holds as long as we sample events from θ_{ref} . From this it follows that the squared error of $1/r(x, z | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ is minimized by the estimated likelihood ratio $1/r_\phi(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ if we sample $(x, z) \sim p(x, z | \theta)$. Combining these two facts, we obtain the loss function [11, ROLR]

$$\begin{aligned} L[r_\phi(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})] &= \left\langle y [r(x, z | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}}) - r_\phi(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})]^2 + \right. \\ &\quad \left. (1 - y) \left[\frac{1}{r(x, z | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})} - \frac{1}{r_\phi(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})} \right]^2 \right\rangle_{(x, z, y) \sim p(x, z, y)}, \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

where $y = 0$ if $(x, z) \sim p(x, z | \theta)$ and $y = 1$ if $(x, z) \sim p(x, z | \theta_{\text{ref}})$.

In practice, we present training samples generated on various hypotheses θ to estimators $r_\phi(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ conditioned on θ . That is, the estimators take θ as input (in addition to the samples x). In this way, they can learn the θ -dependence of the likelihood ratio, making high-dimensional analyses feasible. We update ϕ via back-propagation to minimize Eq. (9).

The score is defined as

$$\mathbf{t}(x | \theta_{\text{ref}}) \equiv \nabla_{\theta} \log p(x | \theta)|_{\theta_{\text{ref}}}.$$

It can be shown that the components of the score vector are the sufficient statistics for $p(x | \theta)$ in the local model approximation, i.e., close to the reference hypothesis θ_{ref} [42]. This effectively means that, sufficiently close to θ_{ref} , the score retains all the information about θ , just as if we were using all the multivariate information. If we were able to estimate the score, we could use it as a summary statistics for the histograms method presented earlier. Following a similar procedure, using Eq. (2),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{t}(x, z | \theta_{\text{ref}}) &\equiv \nabla_{\theta} \log p(x, z | \theta_{\text{ref}}) \\ &= \frac{p(x | z_d) p(z_d | z_s) p(z_s | z_p) \nabla_{\theta} p(z_p | \theta)}{p(x | z_d) p(z_d | z_s) p(z_s | z_p) p(z_p | \theta)} \Big|_{\theta_{\text{ref}}} \quad (10) \\ &= \frac{\nabla_{\theta} p(z_p | \theta)}{p(z_p | \theta)} \Big|_{\theta_{\text{ref}}} = \frac{\nabla_{\theta} |\mathcal{M}(z_p | \theta)|^2}{|\mathcal{M}(z_p | \theta)|^2} \Big|_{\theta_{\text{ref}}}, \end{aligned}$$

we find that **the joint score is also tractable**. Identifying $f(x, z)$ in Eq. (7) with $\mathbf{t}(x, z | \theta_{\text{ref}})$, one can show that the loss functional [11, SALLY]

$$L[\mathbf{t}_{\phi}(x | \theta_{\text{ref}})] = \left\langle [\mathbf{t}(x, z | \theta_{\text{ref}}) - \mathbf{t}_{\phi}(x | \theta_{\text{ref}})]^2 \right\rangle_{(x, z) \sim p(x, z | \theta_{\text{ref}})}, \quad (11)$$

when minimized, approximates the true score $\mathbf{t}(x | \theta_{\text{ref}})$.

In practice, we present training samples generated at θ_{ref} to estimators $\mathbf{t}_{\phi}(x | \theta_{\text{ref}})$ and update ϕ by back-propagation to minimize Eq. (11).

We exploited the fact that $r(x, z | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ and $\mathbf{t}(x, z | \theta_{\text{ref}})$ are available from the simulations to define our loss functionals (11) and (9). Now we see how to calculate $r(x, z | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ and $\mathbf{t}(x, z | \theta_{\text{ref}})$ in a feasible way using morphing.

3.2 Morphing

The structure of the SMEFT Lagrangian in Eq. (1) implies that the squared amplitude factorizes as

$$|\mathcal{M}(z_p | \theta)|^2 = \sum_c w_c(\theta) f_c(z_p).$$

This fact implies that we can choose a basis for our parameter space θ_{α} to calculate any probability density $p(z_p | \theta)$. For this, we only need the pre-computed densities $p(z_p)$ at the benchmarks θ_{α} . See Section A.2 for a complete derivation. Crucially, due to the relation between $p(z_p | \theta)$ and the joint likelihood ratio and the joint score (see Eqs. (6) and (10)), we can calculate $r(x, z_p | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ and $\mathbf{t}(x, z_p | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ for any event using morphing, no matter from which parameter hypothesis it was sampled.

3.3 Estimators

Histograms of observables We used histograms of observables as a baseline. The (negative) LLR is approximated using Eq. (3), where we identify $f(x_i)$ with a function that picks a few (one or two) components of x_i .

We now present the neural estimators used. Regardless of architecture, they are divided into log-likelihood ratio (LLR) estimators $r_\phi(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$, when the learning objective is Eq. (9), and score estimators $t_\phi(x | \theta_{\text{ref}})$, when the learning objective is Eq. (11). LLR estimators are *parametrized*, in the sense that they take as input the theory parameters in addition to the data, learning the θ -dependency of $r_\phi(x | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$.

MLP We use MLP architectures as baselines. For LLR regression, the output dimension is always one, whereas for score regressors it is equal to the number of score components, i.e. equal to the number of theory parameters considered. The input data are vectors of event-level physical observables with fixed length padded with non-physical values for missing features and concatenated with the theory parameter vector in the case of LLR regressors. Each event represents an independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) sample.

Transformer The Transformer architecture is chosen to match that of LGATr as closely as possible. See Fig. 5 for a diagram. Transformer *tokens* are the event particles, and their four-momenta p_μ constitute the initial embeddings of the token. The *sequence* dimension is the particles dimension. We *flatten* the batch and particles dimension and use a pointer object to differentiate particles from different events, since only particles within the same event should attend to each other. This results in a block diagonal matrix, which we use for masked (multi-head) self-attention. In the case of LLR regressors, the four-momenta are concatenated with the parameter vector. Another approach to include the theory parameters in the input data would be to add a *global token* per event, containing the theory parameter values and attending to all event particles. This, however, would mean that the initial embedding dimension should be at least the number of parameters, so if this is bigger than 4 we would have to pad the particles' four-momenta with zeros, for example. We choose simple concatenation and leave experiments with global tokens for future work. The output linear head projects the embeddings to the required dimension (always one for LLR regression and equal to the number of parameters for score regression), and we apply mean pooling over the projections. The architecture is then permutation invariant.

LGATr Here, we discuss our implementation of LGATr for the likelihood ratio and score regression tasks. For an introduction to the architecture, see Section A.3. LGATr organizes inputs in multivectors, which have a fixed dimension of 16 and scalars, with dimension 1. To allow for more expressivity, it

Fig. 5: Transformer architecture matching that of LGATr [36]. Operations with dashed borders do not have learnable parameters. See the Transformer column of Table 1 for a formal description of the layers.

uses *multivector channels* and *scalar channels*. The first are copies of multivectors. The latter are simple scalar representations, which are mixed with the x^S grade of the multivectors in the network operations. Inputs and outputs are then organized into two sets: multivectors, with dimension $(\text{batch_dim}, \text{particles_dim}, \text{mv_channels}, 16)$ and scalars, with dimension $(\text{batch_dim}, \text{particles_dim}, \text{s_channels})$. To embed particles as multivectors, we do

$$x_\mu^V = p_\mu, \quad x^S = x_{\mu\nu}^T = x_\mu^A = x^P = 0.$$

We adapt LGATr to regress both scores and likelihood ratios, embedding the particles four-momenta into the components $[1 : 4]$ of multivectors. Although one could come up with more creative ideas, there are two natural ways to use LGATr for regression tasks: 1. For each particle, add as many scalar channels as regression targets and then apply mean pooling over particles of the same event, or 2. add an extra global token per event with as many scalar channels as regression targets. In both cases, the network output is selected to be the learned representation of the corresponding scalar channels. We choose option 1 in our work since the implementation is simpler and leave experiments with option 2 for future work. For LLR regressors, we encode the information on the theory parameter in the x^S grade of the multivectors, adding copies of the particle multivectors as needed. As for the regular Transformer architecture, we flatten the batch and particles dimension and use a pointer to construct a block diagonal matrix, masking the (multi-head) self-attention operation. Note that because we select the network output to be function of only scalar channels, the architecture is Lorentz invariant. See Table 1 in Section A.3 for a layer-wise comparison of LGATr and our Transformer.

3.4 Evaluation

We evaluate our methods on an Asimov dataset sampled according to the parameter hypothesis θ_{test} . In Asimov datasets, events are weighted according to their parton-level weights. In this way, the confidence intervals (CI) obtained

represent *the expected* CI for many event samples. We construct an appropriate parameter grid according to the study and calculate MLE points and confidence intervals using Eq. (4). The performance metrics of our estimators are: 1. the proximity of the MLE to θ_{test} and 2. the width of the confidence interval (the narrower, the more sensitive the estimator is to changes in θ). It is important to remember that while LLR regressors estimate the quantity of interest directly, the output of score regressors is used to construct n -dimensional histograms of the score components, with n equal to the number of components. The negative LLR between different parameter hypothesis and the reference θ_{ref} is approximated using Eq. (3), where we identify $f(x_i)$ with our $t_\phi(x_i | \theta_{\text{ref}})$.

4 Experimental setup

In this section, we present our experimental setup. We perform a one dimensional (1D) and a three-dimensional (3D) analysis, corresponding to the Wilson coefficients c_{Ht} in the first case and $\{c_{Ht}, c_{tW}, c_{tB}\}$ combined in the latter. We have two types of regressors: LLR regressors and score regressors. This two facts result in an experimental grid 2×2 , with 4 combinations of parameter dimensionality and regression task. From now on, we consider the Wilson coefficients divided by the heavy energy scale, so they have dimensions of TeV^{-2} .

4.1 Physics setup

We used simulations of $tZ(q)$ production at the LHC. In particular, we consider the decay process

$$pp \rightarrow tZ\bar{b}j \rightarrow (b\ell_+\nu_\ell)(\ell_+\ell_-)\bar{b}j,$$

where Z decays dileptonically and the top quark decays as $t \rightarrow bW \rightarrow b(\ell_+\nu_\ell)$. We use MADGRAPH5_AMC@NLO v3.5.1 [3] for event generation together with the LHAPDF6 v6.5.4 [15] parton distribution functions set and SMEFTSIM (top- m_W scheme UFO model v.3.0.2) [14]. We include linear and quadratic terms. We shower and hadronize the generated events with PYTHIA v8.313 [10,6] and simulate the detector response with DELPHES v3.5.0 [22]. We use MADMINER v0.9.6 [13] to set up morphing, to construct observables from the event files, and to extract the joint likelihood ratios and scores from simulation files.

Morphing setup We distinguish two sampling setups and detail here the parameter basis chosen for each one. We sample from the different benchmark parameters to produce events $x \sim p(x | \theta_c)$ and use the optimization algorithm of the morphing basis available in MADMINER.

1D study In the one dimensional study, we only consider the operator \mathcal{O}_{Ht} , and therefore $\theta = c_{Ht}$. We sample from the benchmark points

$$\theta_0 = 0.0 \quad \theta_1 = 0.7312 \quad \theta_2 = -0.9666.$$

3D study In the three dimensional study we consider the combined effects of the operators \mathcal{O}_{Ht} , \mathcal{O}_{tW} and \mathcal{O}_{tB} , and therefore $\theta = (c_{Ht}, c_{tW}, c_{tB})$. The parameter basis is available in Section A.4.

Cuts Following the procedure from [1], we apply the following cuts for event selection (at detector level)

$$1 < \text{len}(j) < 9 \quad \text{len}(\ell) == 3 \quad p_{T,\ell_1} \geq 35 \text{ GeV} \quad p_{T,\ell_i} \geq 10 \text{ GeV} \\ p_{T,j_1} \geq 35 \text{ GeV} \quad p_{T,j_i} \geq 25.0 \text{ GeV} \quad |\eta_\ell| < 2.5$$

where $|\eta|$ is the pseudo-rapidity, a measure of the angle between the particle and the beam axis, and p_T is the momentum of the particle in the plane perpendicular to the beam axis. j (ℓ) denotes the list of jets (leptons) available, ordered in decreasing p_T order.

Observables (Inputs) We distinguish two approaches for observables construction after the results of detector simulation: A *feature-based* approach and a *particle-based* approach. In the feature-based approach we use the transverse momenta p_T , azimuthal angle ϕ and pseudorapidity $|\eta|$ of the three leptons and jets, where ϕ is the azimuthal angle in the transverse plane of the detector, filling default non-physical values when these are not available. This results in a 33-dimensional feature vector. In the particle-based approach we include all particles and jets available for each event after cuts, that is, the four-momenta of all three leptons and all available jets per event.

Unweighting and label extraction Events are generated associated with their parton-level weights $w(\theta)$. To obtain i.i.d samples, we resample events with replacement, with probability proportional to their weights, so that $x \sim p(x | \theta)$ (in the large sample limit). We sample $5 \cdot 10^5$ training events, half of which are sampled according to the SM hypothesis. We used 10^4 test events on the SM hypothesis (θ_0) to construct the Asimov datasets in both studies. The simulation-derived training labels, discussed in Section 3.1, are extracted with MADMINER using morphing. In order to reduce statistical fluctuations associated with large event weights, we only sample events at the benchmark points. See Tables 2 and 3 in Section A.5 for a summary of the datasets prior to re-sampling.

4.2 Estimators and training

See Table 7 in Section A.5 for a complete overview of our neural estimators' hyperparameters. We leave an exhaustive hyperparameter optimization for future work. LLR estimators are trained to minimize Eq. (9), while score estimators are trained to minimize Eq. (11). We use Adam as optimizer [28], dropout as regularizer (0.1), and uniform Kaiming as initialization strategy [24]. We use a constant learning rate of 10^{-3} and a batch size of 50 events.

For the histogram baseline, we bin the transverse momenta of the leading lepton and jet creating a 2-dimensional histogram, dividing the range of each observable into 8 bins. The input and output dimensions of the neural estimators are set to match the different experiments requirements. See Tables 4 to 6 in Section A.5 for a complete overview.

4.3 Evaluation

For evaluation of the 1D study, we construct a one dimensional $\{-1.0, 1.0\}$ parameter grid with 21 evenly spaced c_{Ht} values. For the 3D study, we construct a $\{-1.0, 1.0\}^3$ grid with 11 evenly spaced values for the coefficients c_{Ht} , c_{tW} and c_{tB} . For LLR estimators, we regress likelihood ratios for every point in the grid. For the two-dimensional histograms and for our score estimators, we construct one histogram for every grid point and estimate likelihood ratios using Eq. (3). We plot the -2LLR contours corresponding to a 68% confidence region using the 0.68 quantile of the χ_k^2 distribution, adjusting k to the number of parameters of each study. The test Asimov dataset is sampled according to the SM hypothesis in all cases (i.e., the origin of the parameter grid).

5 Results & Discussion

Here we present the results of our experiments. As mentioned in the previous section, the two configurations of the theory parameters and the two regression tasks form an experiment grid 2×2 . However, we found high numerical instability in LLR regressors for the 3D analysis and do not present the results of that particular study.

Throughout this section, tighter confidence intervals (centered around the SM point) indicate better performance.

5.1 One dimensional analysis: score regression

Fig. 6 shows the results for the 1D study using score regressors. The neural estimators achieve slightly tighter constraints in c_{Ht} , visualized more clearly in Fig. 6b, but the improvements are not very significant.

This indicates that, at least in this simplified physics setup, the isolated effects of just one Wilson coefficient are well captured by traditional methods, and there is nothing much to gain from multivariate methods. In particular, score regressors have small numerical variability, as shown by the shadowed regions in Fig. 6.

5.2 One dimensional analysis: LLR regression

Fig. 7 shows the results for the 1D study using LLR regressors. Compared to score regression, all estimators show increased numerical instability, reflected

Fig. 6: *Left*: Expected negative LLR scans as a function of the c_{Ht} Wilson coefficient for score regressors and the 2D histogram. The results are obtained taking the average predictions of 3 independently trained estimators, and shadows represent the $\pm 1\sigma$ regions. *Right*: We show the 68% (solid) and the 95% (dashed) CI for each estimator.

in the uncertainty bands in Fig. 7a. Despite this variance, the LLR estimators provide improved constraints with respect to the 2D histogram. In this case, the differences between the neural estimators become more apparent. Attention-based architectures yield slightly tighter constraints than the MLP, indicating an improved ability to model the parameter dependence of the likelihood ratio.

Overall, these results confirm the expected larger statistical fluctuations of the LLR regressors as opposed to the score regressors.

5.3 Three-dimensional analysis: score regression

The results of the three-dimensional analysis using score regression are shown in Fig. 8. We present all two-dimensional projections of the $\{c_{Ht}, c_{tW}, c_{tB}\}$ parameter space. For each point in a given two-dimensional slice, the likelihood ratio is evaluated at the MLE of the remaining parameter. In this higher-dimensional parameter setting, the advantages of multivariate estimators become more clear, especially for the Transformer and the LGATr. They produce more centered and more constrained confidence regions. This findings suggest that the potential of the presented architectures is uncovered as the dimension of the theoretical parameters grows.

5.4 Discussion

We find that score regression is substantially more stable than LLR regression, particularly in higher-dimensional parameter spaces. This, along with the fact

Fig. 7: *Left*: Expected negative LLR scans as a function of the c_{Ht} Wilson coefficient for LLR regressors and the 2D histogram. The results are obtained taking the average predictions of 3 independently trained estimators, and shadows represent the $\pm 1\sigma$ regions. *Right*: We show the 68% (solid) and the 95% (dashed) CI for each estimator.

that it aligns better with the current inference approach at the LHC, makes it a preferred candidate over LLR regression. We also note that neural estimators offer only marginal benefits in simple one dimensional problems, with the improvements becoming more relevant in the high-dimensional analysis. This last fact also applies to the comparison between self-attention-based architectures and the MLP. Although LGATr does show slightly tighter constraints than the Transformer, more work would be needed to conclude whether equivariance plays an important role in the parameter constraints task.

6 Limitations of the study and future work

The analyses presented in this work are subject to several limitations. The physical scenario considered is very simplified: we do not include the effects of background processes or nuisance parameters. Moreover, realistic SMEFT analyses typically involve a significantly larger number of Wilson coefficients. Extending to higher-dimensional parameter spaces will introduce additional challenges in terms of training stability and computational cost.

On the machine learning side, the architectural and training choices were not exhaustively optimized. Hyperparameters were selected to allow a consistent comparison between estimators rather than to maximize performance. We leave alternative design choices, such as different parameter encodings, the use of global tokens, and different loss functions, for future work.

Fig. 8: Expected negative LLR contours at 68% confidence region by the score estimators and 2D histogram for the 3D scan involving the set of Wilson coefficients $\{c_{Ht}, c_{tW}, c_{tB}\}$.

A further limitation concerns the numerical stability of likelihood ratio regressors. In higher-dimensional analyses, these estimators exhibited large fluctuations and did not yield reliable results. Morphing-aware estimators or derivative learning are potential strategies to address this issue [8]. Finally, while LGATr shows slightly improved performance compared to the non-equivariant Transformer, the impact of Lorentz equivariance on parameter inference cannot be conclusively assessed within the scope of this study. More extensive studies across different processes would be required to clarify its role.

7 Conclusions

In this work, Transformer architectures were explored for neural simulation-based inference of SMEFT parameters at the LHC. Equivariant and non-equivariant models were adapted to regress likelihood ratios and likelihood gradients using simulated event-level data.

The proposed methods were compared with traditional histogram-based approaches and baseline multilayer perceptron architectures in one- and three-dimensional analyses. In the one dimensional case, improvements by neural estimators are only marginal, with no clear differences between architectures, indicating that simple scenarios are already well described by low-dimensional summaries. In the three-dimensional analysis, self-attention-based architectures yield more constrained confidence regions, highlighting their increased sensitivity in higher-dimensional parameter spaces. Further work is needed to conclude whether Lorentz equivariance allows for increased sensitivity to changes in the parameters.

A consistent difference was observed between the two inference strategies: score regressors were found to be more robust, while likelihood ratio regressors struggled to learn the parameter dependence in higher dimensions and exhibited significant numerical instability.

Despite the simplified physical setup, these results demonstrate the potential of Transformer-based architectures as part of a neural simulation-based inference pipeline for SMEFT parameter estimation and motivate further studies in more realistic scenarios.

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A Appendix

A.1 SMEFT effective Lagrangian

The most general SMEFT Lagrangian that: 1. Preserves the field content of the SM, 2. Preserves the symmetries of the SM fields and the way they are realised or broken, and 3. is valid up to energies $E \sim \Lambda$ is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SMEFT}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}} + \frac{1}{\Lambda} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{d5}} c_i^{(5)} \mathcal{O}_i^{(5)} + \frac{1}{\Lambda^2} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{d6}} c_i^{(6)} \mathcal{O}_i^{(6)} + \frac{1}{\Lambda^3} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{d7}} c_i^{(7)} \mathcal{O}_i^{(7)} + \dots$$

The effective field theory (the SM in this case) can then reliably describe processes with momentum transfer $E \ll \Lambda$. This is effectively a Taylor expansion of the SM Lagrangian valid for energies E much below the new physics scale Λ . Λ acts as an expansion parameter, and higher order terms are suppressed by higher powers of Λ .

It can be shown that no operator with odd mass dimension can preserve both baryon number and lepton number [25]. Baryon number and lepton number conservation are accidental symmetries of the SM, and within the confines of the energy regime considered ($E \ll \Lambda$ at the LHC), SMEFT analyses discard these operators to ensure consistency with observed processes.⁴ After this consideration, we truncate the series to dimension 6 operators, since they give the leading order corrections.

A.2 Morphing

The structure of the SMEFT Lagrangian in Eq. (1) implies that the squared amplitude factorizes as

$$|\mathcal{M}(z_p | \theta)|^2 = \sum_c w_c(\theta) f_c(z_p),$$

which for the simple case of just one parameter of interest expands to

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{M}(z_p | \theta)|^2 &= |\mathcal{M}_{\text{SM}}(z_p) + \theta \mathcal{M}_{\text{BSM}}(z_p)|^2 = \\ &= \underbrace{1}_{w_0(\theta)} \underbrace{|\mathcal{M}_{\text{SM}}(z_p)|^2}_{f_0(z_p)} + \underbrace{\theta}_{w_1(\theta)} \underbrace{2\text{Re}\mathcal{M}_{\text{SM}}^\dagger(z_p)\mathcal{M}_{\text{BSM}}(z_p)}_{f_1(z_p)} \\ &+ \underbrace{\theta^2}_{w_2(\theta)} \underbrace{|\mathcal{M}_{\text{BSM}}(z_p)|^2}_{f_2(z_p)}. \end{aligned}$$

This polynomial dependency on the theory parameters makes possible a very “cheap” sampling strategy. To see that, we note that the differential and total

⁴ In practical terms, we want B/L conservation to be consistent with our observations of LHC processes, such as massless neutrinos and proton stability ($\tau_p > 10^{34}$ years).

cross sections (at the parton level) also factorize as (using Eq. (5))

$$\frac{d\sigma(z_p | \theta)}{dz_p} = \sum_c w_c(\theta) f_c(z_p) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma(\theta) = \sum_c w_c(\theta) \int dz_p f_c(z_p),$$

which in turn implies that

$$p(z_p | \theta) = \frac{1}{\sigma(\theta)} \frac{d\sigma(z_p | \theta)}{dz_p} = \sum_c \frac{w_c(\theta)}{\sigma(\theta)} f_c(z_p) \equiv \mathbf{w}^T(\theta) \cdot \mathbf{f}(z_p). \quad (12)$$

For a given number of basis points θ_a equal to the number of terms in the polynomial, M , we have

$$p(z_p | \theta_a) = \sum_{c=1}^M \frac{w_c(\theta_a)}{\sigma(\theta_a)} f_c(z_p) \quad \text{for } a = 1, \dots, M.$$

In matrix notation

$$\mathbf{p}(z_p) = \mathbf{W} \cdot \mathbf{f}(z_p) \iff \mathbf{W}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{p}(z_p) = \mathbf{f}(z_p),$$

where $\mathbf{p}(z_p)$ is a vector of probability densities, one for each benchmark θ_a , and $\mathbf{f}(z_p)$ is a vector of functions of the squared amplitude, one for each term of the polynomial. \mathbf{W} is an invertible square matrix. Substituting this result into Eq. (12)

$$p(z_p | \theta) = \mathbf{w}^T(\theta) \cdot \mathbf{W}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{p}(z_p).$$

That is, once we have chosen a basis for our parameter space, or set of benchmark points, θ_a , **we can calculate any probability density $p(z_p | \theta)$ using the precomputed $\mathbf{p}(z_p)$ at the benchmarks θ_a** without needing to run any additional simulations. Crucially, because of the relation between $p(z_p | \theta)$ and the joint likelihood ratio and the joint score (see Eqs. (6) and (10)), we can calculate $r(x, z_p | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ and $t(x, z_p | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ for any event using morphing, no matter from which parameter hypothesis it was sampled: consider an event (at parton level) z_p sampled according to θ_{ref} and the joint likelihood ratio $r(z_p | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$. The denominator of $r(z_p | \theta, \theta_{\text{ref}})$ is available from the simulator and the numerator is calculated using morphing.

A.3 LGATr

The Lorentz Geometric Algebra Transformer (LGATr) is a Transformer architecture designed to provide a strong inductive bias for particle physics data. It builds on top of the Geometric Algebra Transformer (GATr) [12], a Transformer architecture equivariant to $E(3)$, the symmetry group of 3D Euclidean space. The key idea is to embed the original vector space of interest V into a higher dimensional space $\mathbb{G}(V)$ with an extra composition law, the geometric product. A generic element of this algebra is called a multivector. It represents different objects and transformations of the original vector space V . In particle

physics, examples of such objects are particle four momenta p_μ , which transform as vectors under Lorentz boosts and rotations,⁵ and particle identification (PID), which is Lorentz invariant. In 3D, examples of such objects are points, direction vectors, and rotations (matrices). For LGATr, the vector space $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ with the metric $g = \text{diag}(1, -1, -1, -1)$ is embedded in the spacetime algebra $G_{1,3}$. Using as a basis for the vector space the four real vectors γ^μ , which satisfy $\{\gamma^\mu, \gamma^\nu\} = 2g^{\mu\nu}$, higher order elements of the algebra are created ($\sigma^{\mu\nu}$, γ^5). Any multivector in the algebra is then represented by as a sum of its grade projections weighted by the corresponding order objects

$$x = x^S 1 + x_\mu^V \gamma^\mu + x_{\mu\nu}^B \sigma^{\mu\nu} + x_\mu^A \gamma^\mu \gamma^5 + x^P \gamma^5 \quad \text{with} \quad \begin{pmatrix} x^S \\ x_\mu^V \\ x_{\mu\nu}^B \\ x_\mu^A \\ x^P \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{16}.$$

By adapting the layers of a regular Transformer architecture [40] and working with multivectors as defined above, LGATr satisfies

$$\text{LGATr}(\Lambda(x)) = \Lambda(\text{LGATr}(x)),$$

where Λ represents a Lorentz group transformation. In summary, LGATr embeds Lorentz equivariance directly into a Transformer architecture through geometric algebra on Minkowski spacetime, making sure that the model's inputs and outputs transform consistently under Lorentz boosts and rotations. This reduces the need for the model to learn frame dependent variability from data and aligns the learned latent representations with the underlying physics symmetries. Although we are not using this feature, LGATr allows for Lorentz symmetry breaking. For example, by adding a global (reference) multivector token to each event with $x^V = (0, 0, 0, 1)$ we favor a particular beam direction, breaking invariance under rotations around the x - and y -axes.

⁵ Under a Lorentz boost along the z axis (using $c = 1$), $t' = \gamma(t - \beta z)$, $z' = \gamma(z - \beta t)$, $x' = x$ and $y' = y$, where $\beta = v$ and $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$, v being the relative velocity between the original and transformed coordinate frames.

Table 1: Comparison of Transformer and L-GATr layers. While in LGATr c represents the (MV or scalar) channel dimension, in the Transformer it represents the *embedding* dimension. $\langle \cdot \rangle_k$ represents the grade k MV projection, n_t the number of tokens in the sequence and μ_x^c and σ_x^c the regular mean and standard deviation across the embedding dimension respectively. Adapted from [36].

Layer type	Transformer	LGATr
Linear(x)	$vx + w$	$\sum_{k=0}^4 v_k \langle x \rangle_k + \sum_{k=0}^4 w_k \gamma^5 \langle x \rangle_k$
Attention(q, k, v) _{ic}	$\sum_{j=1}^{n_t} \text{Softmax}_j \left(\sum_{c'=1}^{n_c} \frac{q_{ic'} k_{jc'}}{\sqrt{n_c}} \right) v_{jc}$	$\sum_{j=1}^{n_t} \text{Softmax}_j \left(\sum_{c'=1}^{n_c} \frac{\langle q_{ic'}, k_{jc'} \rangle}{\sqrt{16n_c}} \right) v_{jc}$
LayerNorm(x)	$\gamma \frac{x - \mu_x^c}{\sqrt{\sigma_x^c + \epsilon}} + \beta$	$x \left[\frac{1}{n_c} \sum_{c=1}^{n_c} \sum_{k=0}^4 \langle x_c \rangle_k, \langle x_c \rangle_k + \epsilon \right]^{-1/2}$
Activation(x)	GELU(x)	GELU($\langle x \rangle_0$) x
GP(x, y)	-	xy

A.4 3D study parameter basis

$$\begin{aligned}
 \theta_0 &= (0.0, 0.0, 0.0) & \theta_1 &= (-0.864, 0.107, -0.903) & \theta_2 &= (-0.399, 0.972, 0.689) \\
 \theta_3 &= (0.724, 0.529, 0.1) & \theta_4 &= (0.063, 0.194, -0.847) & \theta_5 &= (0.904, -0.826, 0.314) \\
 \theta_6 &= (0.426, -0.670, 0.795) & \theta_7 &= (-0.238, -0.252, 0.770) & \theta_8 &= (-0.999, -0.350, -0.856) \\
 \theta_9 &= (0.062, 0.978, -0.710)
 \end{aligned}$$

A.5 Experimental setup tables

Table 2: Dataset sizes for the different benchmark points in the 1D study.

Benchmark	Training set	Test set
θ_0	1,252,787	313,197
θ_1	617,976	154,494
θ_2	593,884	148,471

Table 3: Dataset sizes for the different benchmark points in the 3D study.

Benchmark	Training set	Test set
θ_0	627,457	156,865
θ_1	309,181	77,296
θ_2	281,175	70,294
θ_3	308,980	77,245
θ_4	308,196	77,049
θ_5	307,480	76,870
θ_6	306,957	76,740
θ_7	282,273	70,569
θ_8	309,603	77,401
θ_9	307,060	76,765

Table 4: Number of multivector (MV) channels and scalar channels for different studies and regression tasks combinations in LGATr.

Study	Regression task	Nr. of MV channels	Nr. of scalar channels
1D	Score	1	1
	LLR	1	1
3D	Score	1	3
	LLR	3	1

Table 5: Number of input channel dimensions and output projection dimensions for the Transformer architecture for each experimental setup.

Study	Regression task	Input channel dim.	Output projection dim.
1D	Score	4	1
	LLR	4 + 1	1
3D	Score	4	3
	LLR	4 + 3	1

Table 6: Number of input features and output projection dimensions for the MLP architecture for each experimental setup.

Study	Regression task	Input features	Output projection dim.
1D	Score	33	1
	LLR	33 + 1	1
3D	Score	33	3
	LLR	33 + 3	1

Table 7: Hyperparameter configurations.

Hyperparameter	LGATr	MLP	Transformer
Number of blocks	2	-	2
Hidden MV channels	8	-	-
Hidden scalar channels	16	-	-
Attention			
Number of heads	8	-	8
Additional Q/K MV channels	0	-	-
Additional Q/K scalar channels	0	-	-
Multi-query	False	-	-
Increase hidden channels	1	-	8
Head scaling	False	-	-
Bias	True	-	True
MLP			
Activation	GELU	GELU	GELU
Hidden layers	1	2	2
Expansion factor	4	4	2
Bias	True	True	True